

Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

TURNkey

Deliverable D4.9

Software for improved procedures for rapid mapping of earthquake shaking, including adjustment factors for local site effects (RRE)

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LIST OF PARTNERS

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EMSC	Euro-Mediterranean Seismological Centre	France
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EUC	Fondazione Eucentre	Italy
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BUW	Bauhaus-Universität Weimar	Germany
UA	Universidad de Alicante	Spain
ARU	Anglia Ruskin University Higher Education Corporation	UK
UNIBG	Università degli Studi di Bergamo	Italy
UCL	University College London	UK
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YET	YetItMoves S.r.l.	Italy
GMP	Gempa GmbH	Germany
NOA	National Observatory of Athens	Greece
NTC	Nutcracker Research Ltd.	UK
B80	Beta 80 SpA	Italy
Sim	Siminn hf.	Iceland
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GLOSSARY

Acronym	Description
BN	Bayesian Network
GMICE	Ground Motion Intensity Conversion Equation
GMM	Ground Motion Model
MLS	Minimum Link Set
PGA	Peak Ground Acceleration

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This brief technical report details the code and data structure of the software that has been developed by BRGM for the rapid updating of damage and loss estimates (see Figure 1-1), to be used in the TURNkey platform. The software has the following features:

- propagation of uncertainties, from the ground-shaking estimates to the damage computation;
- use of strong-motion measures from seismic stations and damage identification of components as sources of observation;
- integration of site effects through amplification factors;
- estimation of damage distribution and casualty rates in built areas;
- estimation of the connectivity loss of road networks;
- generation of shape files and damage/loss statistics.

Figure 1-1: Overview of the Bayesian code for the rapid loss updating

2 CODE OVERVIEW

The Bayesian approach for the derivation of shake-maps has been developed by BRGM as a Python/Matlab/R code, which is detailed in the following sub-sections. The computation process is illustrated through an arbitrary earthquake scenario in TB-2 (Pyrenees area, Luchon Valley).

2.1 Structure of the code

Figure 2-1: Structure of the Python files required for shake-map computation.

2.2 Input data

2.2.1 'Static' data ('Input\' folder)

2.2.1.1 Building exposure dataset ('Input\BDG\' folder)

+ built_areas_shape.shp: contour of the municipalities (built areas). The ID field is necessary to identify the built areas and plot them in the outputs (see Figure 2-2).

ID	Nom_Dépa	Nom_Commune	INSEE_Comm
1	HAUTE-GARONNE	ANTIGNAC	31010
2	HAUTE-GARONNE	ARGUT-DESSOUS	31015
3	HAUTE-GARONNE	ARLOS	31017
4	HAUTE-GARONNE	ARTIGUE	31019
5	HAUTE-GARONNE	BACHOS	31040
6	HAUTE-GARONNE	BAGNERES-DE-LUCHON	31042
7	HAUTE-GARONNE	BAREN	31046
8	HAUTE-GARONNE	BENQUE-DESSOUS-ET-DESSUS	31064
9	HAUTE-GARONNE	BEZINS-GARRAUX	31067
10	HAUTE-GARONNE	BILLIERE	31068

Figure 2-2: Attribute table of built_areas_shape.shp.

+ Vulnerability Buildings.xlsx: vulnerability information on the different built areas. Required fields are: ID (ID of the built area), Buildings (number of buildings) and Vi (vulnerability index).

ID	Buildings	Vi	Class
1	70,31	0,68	1
2	74,53	0,66	2
3	114,14	0,70	3
4	35,18	0,77	4
5	33,97	0,70	3
6	1787,08	0,70	3
7	20,10	0,60	5
8	39,25	0,65	6
9	69,09	0,66	7
10	23,62	0,68	1

Figure 2-3: Contents of the file Vulnerability_Buildings.xlsx.

+ Population Buildings.xlsx: population information on the different built areas. Required fields are: ID (ID of the built area) and N_population (number of people).

ID_commune	N population
1	114,0215
2	30,2145271
3	88,1884998
4	35,1275398
5	25,759144
6	2568,15787
7	5,5321101
8	15,2544333
9	52,270958

Figure 2-4: Contents of the file Population_Buildings.xlsx.

2.2.1.2 Road network dataset ('Input\RDN\ ' folder)

+ RDN_NODES.shp: list of nodes composing the road network. Required fields are: ID (ID of the node), LAT (latitude) and LON (longitude).

	ID	LAT	LON
1	1	42,86508211962...	0,750081638064...
2	2	42,86492418707...	0,749843171134...
3	3	42,91585497474...	0,691905928164...
4	4	42,91544889505...	0,691848640790...
5	5	42,86617647953...	0,749073100675...
6	6	42,97406095721...	0,646912098167...
7	7	42,97277415409...	0,646903072083...
8	8	42,89187104651...	0,703271794068...
9	9	42,88392548498...	0,714778041299...
10	10	42,98547341234...	0,636423949148...

Figure 2-5: Attribute table of RDN_NODES.shp.

+ RDN_EDGES.shp: list of edges composing the road network. Required fields are: ID (ID of the edge), START (ID of one extremity nodes), END (ID of the other extremity node), TYPE ('road

segment' = regular non-vulnerable edge, 'bridge' = edge consisting of a vulnerable bridge) and LENGTH (length of the edge in m).

	ACCESS	LANES	TYPE	ROAD_RANK	START	END	LENGTH	ID	▲
1	Always	2 wide lanes	road segment	main	1	2	26,22164017748...	1	
2	Always	2 wide lanes	bridge	main	3	4	45,35370180641...	2	
3	Always	2 wide lanes	road segment	main	5	1	161,8276905928...	3	
4	Always	2 wide lanes	road segment	main	6	7	142,9557101403...	4	
5	Always	2 wide lanes	road segment	main	8	9	1303,535636962...	5	
6	Always	2 wide lanes	road segment	main	10	11	329,7011236224...	6	
7	Always	2 wide lanes	road segment	main	12	13	529,4848818897...	7	
8	Always	2 wide lanes	road segment	main	14	15	19,73749125645...	8	
9	Always	2 wide lanes	road segment	main	16	17	538,3511354759...	9	
10	Always	2 wide lanes	road segment	main	18	8	506,8389150254...	10	

Figure 2-6: Attribute table of RDN_EDGES.shp.

+ TAZ Centroid built areas.shp: list of centroids corresponding to the built areas. Required fields are: ID (ID of the built area), join_ID (ID of the closest road network node), join_LAT (latitude of the closest road network node) and join_LON (longitude of the closest road network node).

ID	▲	Nom_Départ	Nom_Commune	INSEE_Comm	join_ID	join_LAT	join_LON	distance
1	1	HAUTE-GARON...	ANTIGNAC	31010	391	42,82925014105...	0,599401370580...	0,011113443968...
2	2	HAUTE-GARON...	ARGUT-DESSOUS	31015	496	42,89594495322...	0,710733185185...	0,005656475378...
3	3	HAUTE-GARON...	ARLOS	31017	8	42,89187104651...	0,703271794068...	0,019782983053...
4	4	HAUTE-GARON...	ARTIGUE	31019	363	42,82845167414...	0,620896652539...	0,019278593566...
5	5	HAUTE-GARON...	BACHOS	31040	198	42,89702454535...	0,615711692817...	0,012687598668...
6	6	HAUTE-GARON...	BAGNERES-DE...	31042	437	42,73477287312...	0,629155968537...	0,002338980077...
7	7	HAUTE-GARON...	BAREN	31046	418	42,86748071276...	0,619407579989...	0,015557684300...
8	8	HAUTE-GARON...	BENQUE-DESS...	31064	595	42,82541856979...	0,548142575148...	0,007795393653...
9	9	HAUTE-GARON...	BEZINS-GARRA...	31067	182	42,93298246076...	0,696832099675...	0,006465128069...
10	10	HAUTE-GARON...	BILLIERE	31068	372	42,81145354776...	0,527653895805...	0,004724326482...

Figure 2-7: Attribute table of TAZ_Centroid_built_areas.shp.

+ Fragility Function Bridges.xlsx: fragility functions assigned to the road bridges. Required fields are: Id (ID of the road edge corresponding to the bridge), Lat (latitude of the bridge), Lon (longitude of the bridge), mu1 (median of the fragility function, in g), beta1R (standard deviation of the fragility function, part related to aleatory uncertainty), beta1M (standard deviation of the fragility function, part related to epistemic uncertainty) and typo (indicator for bridges that are in the same typology, i.e. using the same fragility function).

Id	Lat	Lon	mu1	beta1R	beta1M	mu2	beta2	mu3	beta3	typo
545	42,8623665	0,7481005	0,669	0,234692884	0,1355	0,755	0,306	1,057	0,429	1
546	42,8492065	0,7357005	0,79	0,681561993	0,3935	1,524	1,518	2,879	2,867	2
2	42,915652	0,6918775	0,11	0,173205081	0,1	0,2	0,05	0,3	0,08	3
486	42,9728235	0,64737	0,669	0,234692884	0,1355	0,755	0,306	1,057	0,429	1
527	42,8838145	0,714911	0,669	0,234692884	0,1355	0,755	0,306	1,057	0,429	1
529	42,8817065	0,71742	0,669	0,234692884	0,1355	0,755	0,306	1,057	0,429	1
482	42,985605	0,636202	0,669	0,234692884	0,1355	0,755	0,306	1,057	0,429	1
480	42,989788	0,6323495	0,669	0,234692884	0,1355	0,755	0,306	1,057	0,429	1
476	42,9933995	0,630651	0,669	0,234692884	0,1355	0,755	0,306	1,057	0,429	1

Figure 2-8: Contents of the file Fragility_Function_Bridges.xlsx.

2.2.1.3 Soil model ('Input\soil_model' folder)

+ soil.tif: Raster file containing information on the soil amplification factors to apply to the ground motion parameters.

2.2.2 'Dynamic' data

+ OBS.mat: Matlab dataset containing the following variables:

- im_coord: coordinates (longitude, latitude) of ground-motion measurements.
- im_val: value of the ground-motion measurements
- dam_id: ID of the road edges where the bridges' damage states have been identified;
- dam_val: value of the identified damage states (0 = survival, 1 = failure).

2.2.3 Modelling data (optional)

+ uniqueLinkset XXX YYY.mat: Matlab dataset containing the composition of MLSs (connectivity analysis between XXX and YYY), defined by the IDs of the Super-Nodes (see Deliverable Report D4.8 for more details). The search for all MLSs in a network may take a very long time with the recursive algorithm, therefore it may be best to pre-process this step and load the list of MLSs when needed.

[10002 10003 10021 10030 10014 10013 10028 10012]
[10002 10033 10003 10021 10030 10014 10013 10028 10012]
[10002 10033 10036 10003 10021 10030 10014 10013 10028 10012]
<i>1x12 double</i>
[10002 10003 10021 10014 10013 10028 10012]
[10002 10033 10003 10021 10014 10013 10028 10012]
[10002 10033 10036 10003 10021 10014 10013 10028 10012]
<i>1x11 double</i>
[10002 10003 10021 10030 10014 10013 10012]
[10002 10033 10003 10021 10030 10014 10013 10012]
[10002 10033 10036 10003 10021 10030 10014 10013 10012]
<i>1x11 double</i>
[10002 10003 10021 10014 10013 10012]
[10002 10033 10003 10021 10014 10013 10012]
[10002 10033 10036 10003 10021 10014 10013 10012]
[10002 10033 10036 10029 10023 10003 10021 10014 10013 10012]

Figure 2-9: Definition of MLSs contained in the dataset uniqueLinkset_10002_10042.mat (connectivity between Super-Nodes 10002 and 10042).

2.3 Output data ('Output/' folder)

+ Built_areas.shp: Shape file of built areas (polygon format) with posterior estimates (mean and standard-deviation) on vulnerability, IM, mean damage grade, proportion of buildings in D1/D2, proportion of buildings in D3/D4/D5, proportion of injured people (P2/P3), proportion of deceased people (P4) for each built area.

ID	postIM_mu	postIM_sig	postD_mu	postD_sig	N_Bldg	N_Pop	postD12_mu	postD12_sig	postD345_mu	postD345_si	postP23_mu	postP23_sig	postP4_mu	postP4_sig
1	0,343456	0,324174	0,478218	0,256782	70,306411	114,021500	0,314313	0,100776	0,026840	0,035118	0,000216	0,000471	0,000068	0,000211
2	-0,117687	0,332346	0,246927	0,137903	74,529167	30,214527	0,194962	0,099675	0,006577	0,009154	0,000041	0,000064	0,000010	0,000018
3	-0,056749	0,366274	0,326434	0,197303	114,141462	88,188500	0,242391	0,110453	0,012601	0,020407	0,000089	0,000218	0,000025	0,000085
4	0,190914	0,351177	0,607983	0,322101	35,175994	35,127540	0,338979	0,106285	0,044133	0,053023	0,000448	0,001128	0,000168	0,000618
5	-0,170969	0,332922	0,278404	0,170611	33,966726	25,759144	0,212406	0,102970	0,009087	0,016060	0,000062	0,000151	0,000017	0,000053
6	0,626835	0,346058	0,750745	0,368778	1787,0808...	2568,157871	0,342118	0,120232	0,066457	0,067581	0,000771	0,001586	0,000309	0,000891
7	-0,098406	0,335263	0,176900	0,105258	20,100000	5,532110	0,139947	0,084073	0,003481	0,005138	0,000022	0,000035	0,000005	0,000010
8	0,239514	0,298691	0,357450	0,178923	39,254860	15,254433	0,270101	0,104383	0,013636	0,016673	0,000090	0,000139	0,000024	0,000045
9	-0,182231	0,412122	0,236963	0,151587	69,090909	52,270958	0,184818	0,106879	0,006604	0,010590	0,000042	0,000078	0,000011	0,000023
10	0,200099	0,291403	0,387570	0,191945	23,623734	22,290038	0,286454	0,101738	0,016187	0,020238	0,000111	0,000202	0,000031	0,000077

Figure 2-10: Attribute table of Built_areas.shp.

+ Bridges.shp: Shape file (point format) with posterior estimates (mean and standard-deviation) on capacity, IM and damage state of each bridge.

	Id	postP	postIM_mu	postIM_sig	postC_mu	postC_sig
1	2	0,213667	-0,252290	0,415249	0,136513	0,177100
2	110	0,289667	0,341361	0,269714	0,844614	0,758355
3	242	0,009000	-0,284395	0,394014	0,862358	0,308475
4	263	0,558333	0,098089	0,259294	0,051406	0,194586
5	306	0,361667	-0,162430	0,312698	-0,041879	0,166119
6	454	0,021667	0,253592	0,159868	0,808123	0,257203
7	470	0,842000	0,337938	0,266984	-0,057812	0,182097
8	473	0,033667	-0,134414	0,255358	1,082983	0,532410
9	476	0,000333	-0,399179	0,361589	0,741878	0,279378
10	478	0,000000	-0,312308	0,363405	0,746202	0,279168

Figure 2-11: Attribute table of Bridges.shp.

+ MLS.shp: Shape file (polyline format) with posterior estimates of the connectivity of each minimum linkset.

	MLS	postMLS_cty
1	1	0,414667
2	2	0,292000
3	3	0,540333
4	4	0,154000
5	5	0,503333
6	6	0,154000
7	7	0,349667
8	8	0,258000
9	9	0,463000
10	10	0,152000

Figure 2-12: Attribute table of MLS.shp.

+ global damage losses.mat: Matlab dataset containing global posterior estimates for the whole area:

- mean and standard-deviation of the number of buildings in states D1/D2 (light damage);

- mean and standard-deviation of the number of buildings in states D3/D4/D5 (heavy damage/collapse);
- mean and standard-deviation of the number of people in states P2/P3 (requiring hospital care);
- mean and standard-deviation of the number of people in states P2/P3 (deceased);
- probability that the connectivity between the two points of interest is lost (accessibility loss).